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Effectiveness of Video Based Lessons in Teaching of Science At Secondary Schools

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Abstract

The use of technology such as audio-visual aids in the classroom brings innovativeness and catches the attention of learners. The audio-visual modes of teaching not only strikes the auditory and sight senses, but also brings content, media expertise into the classroom for structured and effective learning. The present study intends to test this premise in an experimental format. The homogenous group of subjects (having controlled I.Q) are randomly divided into two groups of 30 students each and one group is treated with audio visual tool and other acts as a controlled group. Based on the treatment data, results are discussed and suggestions and implications are made.

Keywords: Conventional Method of Teaching, Audio-Visual Package, Video based lessons

Teaching is a very significant aspect of education. To reach the educational aims and objectives teaching process play a vital role. Looking to the present learner and learning environment there is a need of innovative teaching technology. This can really help to improve the teaching effectiveness. Chronologically speaking there are two main types of teaching methods namely conventional method of teaching and modern teaching. Different methods of teaching coming under conventional method are lecture method, demonstration, class discussion, group discussion, role play and project method etc. The modern methods make use of technology of teaching and are audio, visual, audio visual, programme instruction or CAI programme. These modern methods of teaching can be used as supplementary in teaching learning process.

The investigators have compared lecture method in conventional method with that of audio visual method in modern method of teaching. This study tries to find the better method between conventional and audio visual. Audio visual aids are instructional devices in which the message can be heard and seen simultaneously. For example, television, video films and documentary films etc. In classroom interaction, the teaching will be more effective and forceful if more senses are involved in the process of teaching and learning. The ideas which cannot be expressed orally can be expressed with the help of audio-visual aids easily. According to Kinder (1954), "Any device which can be used to make the learning experiences more concrete, more realistic more dynamic can be considered audio visual material". The example of such a programme is Television programme on the concept of magnetism in which we hear the content and simultaneously see the pictures. This will give the concrete understanding about the concept. According to the Chinese proverb,

if I listen I forget and if I see I remember. So the students can easily remember the content. Each and every concept cannot be imagined by the students so if they see the process of magnetic force and attraction of iron and magnets, the concept will be more realistic for the learner.

I K Davis, has suggested following five characteristics of audio – visual aids:

- Audio visual aids help in developing perception
- It helps in developing understanding. It is used to exhibit the pupils to acquire correct knowledge
- Audio visual aids help in transfer of training
- These are helpful in acquiring knowledge and providing reinforcement
- Audio – visual aids help in developing retention. They help in facilitating assimilation of the knowledge (Agarwal, 2008).

The conventional or traditional mode of teaching involves teacher, students and some other intervening variable in a class. In conventional or traditional teaching the teacher is an active facilitator who imparts the knowledge to the students and the teacher does not use much teaching aids or technology in his teaching. Teacher performs all the teaching activities and the students are just passive viewers and audience. Usually in conventional method of teaching the lecture method is adopted by the teacher. It is the easiest method of imparting knowledge to the pupils. Teacher makes use of conventional teaching material very conveniently; therefore, this method is more popular as compared to the others. It is intend that in this method, presentation is more emphasized and the pupil function as passive listeners, consequently this create dullness in the classroom as interaction between the pupil and the teacher ceases to occur.

In conventional teaching the equipments used are black board, chalk piece, pointer and teaching aids (if required and only when the equipments are available).

In this research the investigators compared the conventional method with that of audio visual method of teaching to find out the most effective method between these.

Objectives

1. To prepare the audio visual programme in Science subject for 10th standard.
2. To impart the lesson through audio visual method and conventional method.
3. To compare the effectiveness of teaching between conventional with audio visual method.

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for pre test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
2. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for post test-1 of the unit solar energy-1.
3. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for pre test-2 of the unit solar energy-2.

4. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group and experimental group for post test-2 of the unit Solar energy-2.
5. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.
6. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of control group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.
7. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-1.
8. There is no significant difference between the achievement scores of Experimental group for pre test and post test for the unit solar energy-2.

Variables of the study

Controlled variable: Intelligence

Independent variable: Method of teaching viz., conventional method of teaching and audio-visual method of teaching

Dependent variable: Academic achievement of the students

Treatment Groups

Control Group

In this group the teacher was asked to teach the unit in his or her usual manner using minimum teaching aids as done in case of regular classes. This mode of teaching mainly relied upon 'teaching by chalk and talk method' utilising textbooks as supplementary aids. The students activities were curtailed, their emotions, creative thinking was also controlled. In all this method meant very less participation of the students, less usage of teaching aids and there was no scope for students to react. The units selected for this type of teaching were same as that of the experimental group.

Experimental Group

In this method the investigators designed audio-video package on selected unit of 10th standard of Science subject, which were same as that of conventional group. It used audio-video media and involved senses of listening and sight. The class teacher had to put on the DVD or VCR with the AV aid prepared by the investigator. The viewing was to be preceded by pre-viewing activities and followed by certain post-viewing activities, which were suggested in the package. In this mode of teaching the teacher was supposed to make use of video compact disc (VCD) player and television monitor with suitable output for audio. Further, the teachers were given training to handle these equipments along with the conduct of pre-viewing and post-viewing activities specified in the concerned programme.

Preparation of Audio Visual Programme

This is one of the main tools of the study, which was developed by the investigators with the following objectives.

- All the students should learn the Science subject systematically, scientifically and effectively.

- The Science subject should be taught with modern AV aids.
- Almost all sense organs should be involved in the learning process.

Keeping in view the above objectives, the investigators utilized the following primary sources for construction of such tool.

1. Text book of 10th standard Science subject
2. Encyclopaedia of Science and Technology.
3. Animation Films and Video Clips and recording of a structured video programme.

The preparation of audio visual programme is shown in the Fig. 1 and includes following steps.

1. **Conceiving the programme:** This is the first step of preparing video programme in which the investigators conceived and planned whole process and drew flow chart of all the activities which were to be followed for the video lesson preparation. The content, instructional and methodological, technical aspects were planned.
2. **Script Writing:** The investigators wrote the script in consultation with the media expert and referred various books.
3. **Converting to camera script:** After writing the video script the investigators discussed with the producers and media experts regarding the procedure to convert the video script to camera script. The investigators wrote the video script keeping in view use of camera technology.
4. **Vetting and finalizing scripts:** The camera scripts were analyzed from different dimension like, content error was verified, language mistakes were corrected, dialogues were examined, flow of the dialogues was checked, role of character was tested and other required modification were made and lastly the script was finalised.
5. **Identifying the characters and rehearsal:** The investigators visited a nearby school and selected few students who were out spoken, communicative and well aware of content and then script was given to read. Based on good capacity of dialogue delivery characters were finalized. The whole script was given to these characters and they were asked to read thoroughly and get prepared for rehearsal. The rehearsal was made in the classrooms. During rehearsal the investigators corrected the pronunciations of students, style of talking, conversation and taught intricacies of acting required for the programme etc. The participants were informed about dress manners for recording programme.
6. **Recording of Programme:** The recording in the studio was done very systematically. First the rehearsal was made in front of the producer for his satisfaction from technical point of view. Then, the artists were taken for the recording in the studio. During recording the investigators faced few problems like voice matching, acting, style, use of proper dialogues etc. These were corrected and re-recordings were done wherever it was necessary to maintain quality of programme.
7. **Editing:** Editing is backbone of the recording. In editing the media experts removed unnecessary pauses, repetitions, and added the pictures, video clippings animation relevant to the content. The programme was viewed again and again till it was error free.
8. **Try out of the quality of programme:** The investigators showed the video programme to students and teachers in selected school and conducted the achievement test on the students.

Fig. 1: Showing audio visual

Pre- and Post-Viewing Preparation

It is thought that the video scriptwriters (investigators) were concerned only with content of the programme. But they also kept in mind what was needed to be told to the audience prior to and after the programme, so that they can be properly motivated and enlightened and many of the new concepts and ideas would be made clear and meaningful. Therefore, the video scriptwriters and/or producers had prepared support materials and notes on their specific programme with clear cut objectives for pre- and post-viewing activities. These activities helped in enriching learning and fixing learnt material in the minds of students.

Try-out

The Audio Visual package was shown to experts and necessary feedbacks were obtained with respect to the level of language, picture quality, objectives vis-à-vis the content present and logical presentation of the subject matter etc. The feedback from students and experts were incorporated for finalisation of programme.

Details of Software

1. **Name:** Audio Visual Package
2. **Subject:** Science
3. **Unit:** Solar Energy
4. **Level:** Secondary School
5. **Hardware requirement:** Television, Video CD Player, remote or computer etc.
6. **Monitor (VDU):** VCD Player, Television, Loud speaker (based on classroom size)
7. **User Interface:** Remote control, keys on the monitor and CD player
8. **Special Features:** Contains audio-video package for 10th standard SSLC pattern

Validity of the Programme

Content validity: The content selected for the programme was based on the objectives set for the school subject and topic. All the intended points were covered and properly presented in the programme. This shows that the content is valid.

Concurrent validity: The programme content was based on the existing syllabus of SSLC prevailing in Karnataka. This was appropriate for present day needs. Hence, it is concurrent.

Construct Validity: The programme was constructed based on learning theories and media requirement. Interactivity was also in built into it. Hence, it had construct validity.

Face validity: The audio visual programme was a representative of classroom lesson in audio visual format. Hence, it had face validity.

Statistical Techniques used: The investigators used statistical techniques like mean, standard deviation and t-value. The statistical tools given in Best (2010) were referred and following tools and formulae were used for calculations.

$$\text{Mean} = \frac{\sum X}{N}$$

$$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (X_i - \bar{X})^2}{N - 1}}$$

$$t = \frac{\text{Difference of Mean}}{SE}$$

$$\text{Where } SE = \sqrt{\frac{S_1^2}{N_1} + \frac{S_2^2}{N_2}}$$

Data Analysis and Interpretation

H1: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre test 1 of solar energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 1,

Table 1: Showing t-value between Control group and Experimental group for pre test-1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	4.1	1.028	0.262	1.64
Experimental	30	29	4.5	1.002		

*not significant

From Table 1 it is, inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 1.64 and the Table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The Table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H1 is accepted. Hence, it is concluded that there is no significant difference between the means of Control group and experimental group for pre-test score for the unit solar energy 1.

H2: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post test 1 of solar energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 2,

Table 2: showing t-value between Control group and Experimental group for post-test 1

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	7.96	0.85	0.288	29.28
Experimental	30	29	16.4	1.32		

*significant

The Table 2 it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 29.28 and the Table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The Table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H2 is rejected. Hence, it indicates that there is significant difference between the means of Control group and experimental group on post test score on solar energy 1. After observing the means of both the group it can be drawn that the mean score is in favour of experimental. That is after treatment the achievement of Experimental group is better than Control group.

H3: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for pre test 2 of solar energy 2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 3,

Table 3: showing t-value between Control group and Experimental group for pre-test 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	3.93	0.82	0.249	0.935
Experimental	30	29	4.16	1.08		

* not significant

The Table 3 it is inferred that the calculated value of 't' is 0.935 and the Table value of 't' at 0.01 level of significance is 2.756. The Table value of 't' is greater than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H3 is accepted. Hence, it indicates that there is no significant difference between the means of Control group and experimental group.

H4: There is no significant difference between the scores of control group and experimental group for post test 2 of solar energy 2.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 4,

Table 4: Showing t-value between Control and experimental group for post test 2 in the unit solar energy 2

Group	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Control	30	29	10.93	1.048	0.33	15.13
Experimental	30	29	16.03	1.519		

* Significant

The Table 4 indicates that the calculated value of 't' is 15.13 and the Table value at 0.01 level of significance is 2.75. The Table value of 't' is less than the calculated value. Therefore, the null hypothesis H4 is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference between means of Control and Experimental group for post test 2 of Solar Energy 2. Looking at the means it can be inferred that the mean score is in favour of Experimental group. That means after treatment the achievement of Experimental group is better than Control group.

H5: There is no significant difference between mean score of pre-test and post-test of Control group for the unit solar energy 1.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 5.

Table 5: Showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Control group for Solar energy 1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Post-test	30	29	7.96	0.85	0.243	15.86
Pre-test	30	29	4.1	1.028		

*Significant

The Table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 15.86 which is more than the Table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test scores of Control group in solar energy 1. The means of both the scores indicates that Control group students perform well after teaching.

H6: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Control group for the solar energy 2 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 6.

Table 6: Showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Control group for Solar energy2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Post-test	30	29	10.933	1.048	0.243	28.69
Pre-test	30	29	3.933	0.828		

*Significant

The Table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 28.69 which is more than the Table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Control group in solar energy 2 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Control group students perform very well after teaching unit solar energy 2.

H7: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for the solar energy 1 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 7.

Table 7: showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for Solar energy1

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre-test	30	29	4.533	1.008	0.304	38.97
Post-test	30	29	16.4	1.328		

* Significant

The Table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 38.97 which is more than the Table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for solar energy 1 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental group students perform very well after treatment or teaching through audio visual programme.

H8: There is no significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for the solar energy 2 unit.

To test this hypothesis the investigators subjected data obtained to 't' test and the results are given the Table 8.

Table 8: Showing t-value between pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for Solar energy2

Test	N	df	Mean	SD	SE	t-value
Pre-test	30	29	4.166	1.085	0.34	34.80
Post-test	30	29	16.033	1.519		

* Significant

The Table value at 0.01 level is 2.75 and the calculated value is 34.80, which is more than the Table value. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it is inferred that there is significant difference between means of pre-test and post-test of Experimental group for solar energy 2 unit. The means of both the scores indicates that Experimental group students perform very well after treatment or teaching through audio visual programme.

Major Findings

1. There was no significant difference in the achievement of control group and experimental group before giving the experimental treatments for the unit Solar energy-1.
2. The students who learnt solar energy-1 through audio visual method achieved significantly more than those who learnt through conventional method.
3. There was no significant difference in the achievement of control group and experimental group before giving the experimental treatments for the unit Solar energy-2.
4. The students who learnt solar energy-2 through audio visual method achieved significantly more than those who learnt through conventional method.
5. When the students' pre-test and post-test score of control group were compared for the unit Solar energy-1, it is found that there is significant difference between two sets of achievements, which means the control group students have achieved significantly more than the pre-test score, which also means that the conventional method of teaching Science helps the students to achieve score.
6. When taught through the audio visual programme for the unit Solar energy-1, it is found that students achieved significantly more than the pre-test which means the Audio visual programme helped the students to learn better.
7. When the students' pre-test and post-test score of control group was compared for the unit Solar energy-2, it was found that there is significant difference between two sets of achievements which means the control group students have achieved significantly more than the pre-test score which also means that the conventional method of teaching Science also help the students to achieve score.
8. When taught through the audio visual programme for the unit Solar energy-2, it is found that students achieved significantly more than the pre-test which means the Audio visual programme helped the students to learn better.

Suggestion for further Research

The study should be extended both horizontally and vertically to different geographical locations, levels of teaching, subject areas. Comparative studies must be made among different areas listed above. Efforts are also required to be made to find out impact on indigenous languages and technologies like audio, audio-visual, multi-media technologies. There are many such areas, which can be studied for their effectiveness and creative and resourceful investigators are to think further on this area and strengthen use of technology in education.

Conclusion

The present study indicates that the teaching methods, whether conventional or modern technology based, both are effective in teaching science at secondary level. However, there is a significant improvement after

teaching through audio-visual methods over conventional mode. This is indicative that the teachers should not shy away from technology and make a judicious use at all levels of school education. This is the time when media experts, policy makers and educators can sit together and design proper plan for use of audio-visual technology.

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